

UWB Microstrip Line Feeding Planar Modified Circular Antenna

Pillalamarri L.

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Radio Frequency and Microwave Laboratory,
IIT Hyderabad, Telanagana-State, India

Article info:

Paper received: July 5, 2017
The final version of the paper received: December 12, 2017
Paper accepted online: February 28, 2018

Corresponding Author's Address:

laxmanpillalamarri85@gmail.com

Abstract. In this paper we have investigated compact printed semicircular disc monopole antenna, which is basically printed microstrip antenna with etched ground plane for UWB applications. In particular we have simulated very compact semicircular disc monopole antennas for UWB communication. Simple rectangular microstrip line is used for feeding the printed monopole antenna and its frequency bandwidth under -10 dB return loss is ranging from 3 GHz to 11.6 GHz. This compact printed monopole antenna works well for the whole UWB frequency band 3.1–10.6 GHz.

Keywords: UWB, semicircular printed monopole antenna, microstrip line.

1 Introduction

Ultra-Wideband (UWB) commonly refers to signal or system that either has a large relative bandwidth (BW) or a large absolute bandwidth [1–4]. Such a large BW offers specific advantages with respect to signal robustness, information content and/or implementation simplicity. But such systems have some fundamental differences from the conventional narrowband systems. The Federal communications Commission (FCC) has designated the 3.1 to 10.6 GHz band with Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) below -40 dBm/kHz for UWB Communications.

2 Literature Review

Some UWB antennas are much more complex than other existing single band, dual band and multi-band antennas [5, 6]. Most of the UWB monopole antennas are investigated till today is non-planar as in [7, 8] and due to its protruded structure they cannot be integrated with integrated circuits and they are fragile. Few researchers have also studied printed monopole Antennas

In this paper, we will investigate UWB antenna, which is basically a printed microstrip antenna with etched ground plane. First we will investigate in depth the semicircular disk printed monopole antenna for UWB applications. For getting compactness, we have etched the half of the part of circular patch without disturbing the bandwidth as well as antenna parameter. We have used con-

ventional rectangular microstrip lines as feed lines for printed UWB antennas which are properly matched to the antenna impedance. In future we will also investigate other broadband matching techniques to further improve the UWB performance of the printed monopole antennas [9–11]. CAD-FEKO simulation software has been employed for obtaining the simulation results.

3 Research Methodology

This modified UWB monopole antenna is designed directly from the circular disc UWB-Monopole antenna with some modifications in the patch shape as shown in Figure 1. We have used the same FR4 substrate with 4.4 relative permittivity and 1.6 mm thickness. The real part of antenna impedance is exactly 50Ω at 8.5 GHz and 10.8 GHz when the imaginary part of antenna impedance cross zero. The final optimal dimensions of the UWB-monopole antenna are:

- dimensions of patch: radius $r = 12$ mm; metal thickness 0.035 mm;
- dimensions of substrate: $W_1 = 34$ mm; $L_1 = 50$ mm;
- dimensions of ground: $W_2 = 34$ mm; $L_2 = 26$ mm;
- microstrip line: $W_3 = 2.6$ mm; $L_3 = 27.5$ mm, where g is a gap between the ground plane and patch.

After doing an extensive simulation study, we have fixed the dimensions of UWB monopole antenna and the value of g as 1 mm. The antenna impedance, f_{low} , f_{high} and radiation efficiency are tabulated in Table 1. Note that proposed semicircular disc Monopole antenna is more